

Horizon 2020
Programme

Cost/Benefit Analysis

Tool / Technology: Automatic milk feeder for kids (GEA Farm Technology)

Analysis prepared by (country): Estonia

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / Meat / **Both**

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Estonia

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / Housed 4-8 months a year / **Mainly indoors**

Farm grazing area: zero grazing

Species: Sheep / **Goat**

Number of animals: 450-500 goat kids

Breed: Thuringian

Number of staff: 1

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement N° 101000471.

Costs

Initial set-up

- **Capital costs (Large items e.g. a weigh crate, auto-drafter, etc.):**
 €1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000
- **Individual costs (Smaller items e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**
 €1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500
- **Equipment leasing costs (if not purchased):**
 Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500
- **Lifetime of the technology (approximately how long will it last before needing replaced)?**
 1 – 4 weeks 1-6 months 6 – 12 months 1-2 years 2-5 years > 5 years
- **Farm infrastructure requirements:** Decrease Increase No change
- **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology? 60 %**

Running costs

- **Power source requirements (tick all that apply):**
 Not required Mains Battery Solar Other
- **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**
 - **If yes**

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
- **Additional licences or permits required? No / Yes – Annual / Yes – Monthly / Yes - Weekly**
 If yes, cost: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500
- **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription? Yes / No / Not applicable**
 If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500
- **Maintenance / replacement parts:**
 Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know
- **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

Training requirements

- **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**
 If Up to an hour Half day Full day More
 yes, time range?
- **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**
- **Are there additional costs associated with training and/or technical advice? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving.
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.).
- Management decisions for animal groupings.
- Better individual animal management.
- Improved medicine use.
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better.
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.).
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.).
- Increased information on production system.
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location).

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s).
- Improved welfare of the animals(s).
- Additional information on animal behaviour.
- Information on water intake / water availability.
- Information on food intake / food availability.

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices.
- Ease of data transfer to other software.
- Easy to use once installed.

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff .
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)
- Helps to attract new entrants in to the small ruminant industries.

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Consistent quality of milk replacer offered and the means of access. Higher milk intakes of the kids, less scouring, less disease and mortality of the kids. Reduced aggression. Reduced labour costs and time.

Overall summary:

- **Ease of use?** *Scale 1 (Complicated) – 10 (Simple)*
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 **8** 9 10
- **Value for money (for this type of benchmark farm)?** **Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~**
- **Recommend this tool/technology for use on other types of farm?**
Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~
- **Additional comments?**
Mainly for dairy sheep and goat farms. Meat sheep farms would only be suitable for a large number of animals to achieve profitability.
A milk replacer unit that mixes goat milk powder and water and warms it to a temperature that can be determined and regulated by the farmer.

